

STUDY OF BOND STRENGTH OF COMPOSITE AND CONCRETE INTERFACE IN THE REHABILITATION OF CONCRETE STRUCTURES USING POLYMER COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Fiber-reinforced polymer composite materials can be used to replace steel in the external rehabilitation of deteriorating concrete structures. In the present study a specially designed peel test was utilized to characterize the interfacial bond strength of a carbon fiber/epoxy composite and concrete substrate. The fracture energy at the composite and concrete interface was found to increase with the peel angle. It also increased when the crack propagation rate along the interface decreased. The crack was found to propagate mainly through the adhesive while cohesive debonding inside the concrete had a much limited scope. The present experimental results were correlated to results from finite element modeling of the peel test and generally agreed well with the numerical predictions.

INTRODUCTION

The corrosion of the internal steel reinforcement is a major problem with concrete, which is the most widely used construction material. As a means of rehabilitation, steel plates can be externally bonded to the structure. This plating technique has been utilized quite successfully for the past 25 years on all types of concrete structures [1]. However, the corrosion of steel plates continues to be a problem. In fact, adverse environmental conditions pose an even greater hazard to externally bonded steel plates.

Fiber-reinforced polymer composites have good fatigue properties and excellent corrosion resistance. An important characteristic of high strength fibers is that their tensile strength exceeds the tensile strength of steel, but at less than 10% of the weight of steel. The steel plates are difficult to handle in the field and could add significant loads to the structure. The use of polymer composite materials as replacement of steel may overcome these problems in the steel plating process. For example, it was reported that 94kg of steel plates can be replaced with 4.5kg of carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites for bridge strengthening [2].

Although material costs are generally high for a rehabilitation operation using polymer composites, only about 20% of the total costs are dedicated to the purchase of material, while the remainder are labor costs [1]. If the reinforcing material is easy to handle and only simple equipment is required, the use of polymer composites becomes a highly attractive solution for the rehabilitation of deteriorating concrete structures.

When the composite reinforcement sheets are bonded to the tensile surfaces of the concrete members, the adhesive materials must have sufficient toughness to dissipate energy from cracking, and sufficient strength and stiffness to transfer stress between the concrete and the composite reinforcement. The debonding of the reinforcement plate from the concrete structure can be caused by either interfacial crack propagation, plate peel-off due to shear cracks or failure of concrete in shear [3]. The evaluation of interfacial bond strength is thus of primary importance to this composite plating technique.

Although a preliminary experimental study on interfacial bond between polymer composites and concrete members has been conducted using a specially designed peel test [4], there is still relatively little understanding of both the composite-concrete interface and the peel test used for characterization of the bond strength. In the present study, the peel test was performed for carbon fiber-reinforced epoxy composite materials bonded to a concrete substrate. The fracture energy at the composite and concrete interface was characterized. The effects of several experimental parameters, including peel angle and peel rate, on the fracture energy were studied. The failure modes at the interface were also examined.

THE PEEL TEST

A schematic diagram of the peel test setup is illustrated in Figure 1. A thin composite material strip is bonded to a concrete plate and a peel force is applied to the end of the strip at an angle to the concrete substrate. The strain energy release rate G at the composite and concrete interface can be readily calculated from the energy equilibrium as [5]:

$$G = \frac{P}{w}(1 - \cos \alpha) + \frac{P^2}{2w^2tE} \quad (1)$$

where P is the peel force; α is the peel angle; E is the elastic modulus of the composite strip in peel direction; w and t are the width and thickness of the strip, respectively.

A thin strip of the composite adhering to a concrete substrate can be considered as a flexible joint provided that the strip is sufficiently thin and capable of bending sufficiently without cracking. There are several commonly used test methods for evaluation of the interfacial fracture energy at a flexible joint, including peel test, pure shear test and simple extension test [5]. Compared with other test methods, peel test specimens are easy to fabricate and the test is relatively simple to conduct. The peel force is a direct measurement of the interfacial fracture energy using Equation (1) and the bond failure growth can be controlled at a predetermined rate. The mixed mode failure at the interface also represents a failure mode which may be encountered under service conditions.

The peel test fixture used in a previous experimental study [4] was modified and utilized in the present study. It can be seen from Figure 1 that as the cross-head of the test frame moves upward, the composite strip is peeled from the concrete substrate. To ensure that the peel

Figure 1. Schematic Diagram of Peel Test

angle remains at the designated value, the slider on the test fixture has to move from left to right. To account for the force required to move the slider, the composite strip was made to go through the motions of peeling again after being peeled. The friction force recorded was then subtracted from the previously recorded peel force to give the actual peel force. The force was recorded every second by the load cell in a displacement control Instron 1125 test frame and was input to the data acquisition system in a Macintosh computer. The vertical peel displacement was calculated from the cross-head speed. Figure 2 shows a typical load vs displacement plot of the peel test. An average peel force can then be calculated from the curve. Therefore the fracture energy at the composite and concrete interface can be calculated from the peel force using Equation (1).

Figure 2. A Typical Load vs Displacement Curve in the Peel Test (60° Peel Angle, 5.08mm/min Cross-Head Speed)

CHARACTERIZATION OF A COMPOSITE AND CONCRETE INTERFACE

Glass fibers are widely used as reinforcements in composite materials since they are economical to produce. However, their potentially inferior fatigue behavior restricts their use for strengthening concrete structures. Generally, glass fibers maintain only 25% of their total strength up to 10,000,000 cycles, while carbon fibers and aramid fibers maintain 80% and 40% of their respective total strength [6]. Since carbon fibers are approximately twice as stiff as aramid fibers and are less possible to become deterioration than either glass or aramid fibers, their use as reinforcements in polymer composites is favored for concrete structure rehabilitation [7].

In the present study, the composite material was made from FTS-C1-30MP unidirectional carbon fiber tow sheet by Tonen Inc. and D.E.R. 354 epoxy resin by Dow Chemical Company, with Ancamide 2353 curing agent by Air Products & Chemical Inc. The composite material and the pure resin were characterized in the present study using ASTM standard test methods and their properties obtained are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. Material Properties

unidirectional carbon/epoxy composite material	epoxy
$E_{11} = 71.4\text{GPa}$, $E_{22} = 4.8\text{GPa}$, $G_{12} = 3.1\text{GPa}$, $\nu_{12} = 0.32$	$E = 2.6\text{GPa}$, $\nu = 0.39$

The concrete mortar used in the present study was made from cement, sand and water by a ratio of 1:3:0.45 and was allowed to cure at ambient condition. It has a modulus of 21.5GPa under compressive loading. The tensile strength of the concrete mortar is 25.91MPa and the strain at failure is 0.15% [8]. The concrete plates have dimensions of length equal to 228.6mm (9.0in), width equal to 152.4mm (6.0in) and thickness equal to 25.4mm (1.0in). One side of the plate was glass beaded. The mechanical abrasion leads to a nonplanar surface and therefore an increase in the surface area for bonding. The nonplanar surface also promotes mechanical interlocking between the epoxy and the concrete mortar.

The carbon fiber reinforcement was in the form of dry unidirectional fiber fabrics in which the fibers are attached to a glass scrim fabric with a layer of resin adhesive. The tow sheets were cut to strips, with length equal to 330.2mm (13.0in) and width equal to 25.4mm (1.0in). The epoxy was applied to the tow sheet and the pretreated surface of the concrete mortar plate using a paint roller. The wet side of the tow sheet was then placed on the wet surface of the concrete plate and firmly pressed into place to ensure even contact with no air pockets. The backing paper of the tow sheets was then removed and epoxy was applied again. A total of four composite strips were placed side by side on one concrete plate. A 25.4mm (1.0in) long pre-existing crack at the peel front was included in the specimen by inserting a 25.4mm (1.0in) wide strip of plastic sheet between the composite strip and the substrate. The peel test specimens were then allowed to cure at room temperature for at least one week. The average thickness of the cured composite strips, each consisting of one layer of unidirectional fiber tow sheet, is 0.4mm.

The peel test was performed at four different cross-head speeds, i.e., 1.27mm/min (0.05in/min), 2.54mm/min (0.1in/min), 5.08mm/min (0.2in/min) and 12.7mm/min (0.5in/min). At least three composite strips were peeled at one cross-head speed for one peel

angle. A typical curve of peel force vs cross-head movement has been shown in Figure 2. Figure 3 shows the average peel forces at various cross-head speeds for three peel angles, i.e., 30°, 45° and 60°. It can be seen that the cross-head speed had an effect on the peel force, especially at smaller peel angle. When the cross-head speed decreased, the peel force obtained increased, although not significantly.

Figure 3. Peel Force for Three Peel Angles at Various Cross-Head Speeds

As mentioned above, one of the advantage of the present peel test is that the interfacial failure growth can be controlled at a predetermined rate. An experimental parameter, namely, peel rate, was defined [8] and it is in fact the crack propagation speed along the composite and concrete interface. The fracture energy at the composite and concrete interface, calculated from Equation (1), is shown in Figure 4 as a function of the peel rate, the effect of the peel rate being similar to that of cross-head speed on the peel force. When the peel rate decreased, the fracture energy increased. The fracture energy also depends on the peel angle, as shown in Figure 5. When peel angle increased, the fracture energy increased. This observation agrees with other experimental studies [4,9].

Figure 4. Fracture Energy at the Composite and Concrete Interface as a Function of Peel Rate

Figure 5. Fracture Energy at the Composite and Concrete Interface as a Function of Peel Angle at a Cross-Head Speed of 5.08mm/min

Figure 6 shows a typical surface (12X) of a composite strip after being peeled from the concrete substrate. Three failure modes can be seen in the figure, namely, peel inside the mortar, peel through the adhesive and peel at the tow sheet surface. There is no significant difference between strip surfaces peeled at different peel angle or under different peel rate. However, on all the composite strips examined, only a little amount of mortar was peeled, the latter two failure modes being the dominant ones. That is, the cohesive debonding inside the concrete substrate happened in a very limited scope. The crack propagated mainly through the adhesive.

Figure 6. A Typical Surface of Composite Strip Peeled From the Concrete

CORRELATION WITH A NUMERICAL ANALYSIS OF THE PEEL TEST

A comprehensive experimental study is very expensive and time-consuming. However, a combined analytical and experimental investigation can be much more efficient and economical. Numerical analyses could be used to screen various experimental parameters and only the most critical of these parameters then need to be verified experimentally. As a parallel effort to the present experimental study, a finite element analysis was performed to model the peel test and study crack propagation along the composite and concrete interface [10,11]. Four different crack propagation paths were considered, namely, interfacial debonding between the composite and the adhesive, between the adhesive and the concrete, cohesive debonding inside the adhesive, and inside the concrete substrate. It should be noted that no effects of different crack propagation paths are taken into account in Equation (1). Also, mode I and mode II components of the fracture energy can not be separated, Equation (1) being able to calculate the total fracture energy only.

The numerical modeling [11] predicted that the crack propagation along the interface between composite strip and adhesive layer yields the lowest strain energy release rate, and therefore is the most possible failure path. The difference between strain energy release rates at the composite-adhesive interface, at the adhesive-concrete interface and inside the adhesive was also predicted to be not significant. Cohesive debonding inside the concrete substrate is the least possible path. Due to flaws in materials, the actual crack propagation path may well be a mix of all these four paths and the measured peel force and therefore the fracture energy may oscillate during the peeling. In fact, this was often observed in the present experimental study, as shown in a typical load vs displacement curve in Figure 2. The analytical prediction also agrees with the present experimental results that most of the failures propagated through the adhesive instead of the concrete substrate. Also the prediction that no much difference between strain energy release rates at three crack propagation paths other than inside the concrete agrees with the fact that failure through the adhesive and failure at the fiber tow sheet surface are almost equally possible, as shown in Figure 6.

The analytical results also suggested that for a smaller peel angle the difference is little between strain energy release rates at all possible crack propagation paths. However, for a larger peel angle, the difference is more significant. This means that for a smaller peel angle the cohesive debonding inside the concrete substrate is more possible than for a larger peel angle. However, in the present experimental study, the amount of mortar peeled from the substrate did not appear to depend on the peel angle.

The finite element analysis can calculate mode I and mode II components of the fracture energy directly. However, it can not be done in the closed-form solution, i.e. Equation (1). In a previous experimental study [4,8], a data reduction scheme [9] was used to separate mode I and mode II components of the fracture energy at the composite and concrete interface. This scheme was found to yield inconclusive results that could lead to erroneous conclusions in some cases [11]. Further numerical study is currently underway to find a ratio of the two components based on material properties and peel geometry.

CONCLUSIONS

In the present study, a specially designed peel test was used to characterize the bond strength between a carbon fiber/epoxy composite and concrete substrate. The interfacial fracture

energy was measured for various peel angles and peel rates. When the peel angle increased, or when the peel rate decreased, the fracture energy at the composite and concrete interface was found to increase. The examination of the composite strip surface after being peeled from the concrete substrate revealed that most of the failures happened at the adhesive and only a little amount of mortar was peeled from the substrate. The present experimental results agreed well with the predictions of a finite element analysis of the peel test.

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